

THE POWER OF SIXTY WORDS IS THE MAIN SONG OF THE PEOPLE OF THE COUNTRY ANTHEM OF INDEPENDENCE AND PROSPECT

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ABSTRACT

This article talks about the anthem of independence and perspective, which is the main song of the people of the country, the power of sixty words.

Keywords: independence, anthem, perspective, melody, melody, composer, poet.

No matter which era of the history of our statehood, whose roots go back 3,500 years, we witness that the symbols of the nation, symbols of the Motherland are considered dear and sacred. At every stage of development and history, state symbols and emblems are not only a means of implementing politics, but at the same time they have acquired a huge social and spiritual significance. Our nation's idea of building an independent and strong state, its potential, and its commitment to universal human values are first of all expressed in state symbols and emblems. For this reason, sacred symbols and symbols were greatly honored in the socio-political and spiritual life of our ancestors. The idea of building a great state was also expressed in the symbols and emblems of our state, adopted in the early days of independence. The National Anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted on December 10, 1992 at the 11th session of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan reflects the will, thinking, potential, pride and mood of our people that have not faded over the centuries, the pride of building a great and holy independent Motherland. the mother is reflected.

Here, since December 10, 1992, when our national anthem, which is a symbol of the state sovereignty of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is played, we all stand and listen to it, and sing along if we can. When our children, who went to pre-school education institution without speaking, come home and recite "Serkuoyosh" in their sweet "dialect", our eyes involuntarily bring tears to our eyes. We are thankful that we have such a Motherland, Fatherland, and we praise it all the time.[1]

The Constitution, Presidency, Flag, Coat of Arms, Anthem are the state symbols of independent Uzbekistan. They are our symbols with legal force. Emblems and symbols embody the glory, pride, historical memory and noble aspirations of the people of Uzbekistan. Non-recognition of any of them is considered as a sign of non-

recognition of the Constitutional state. The spiritual and educational power of our symbols is extremely high. Honoring them means strengthening one's dignity, faith in one's homeland and one's self.

Anthem is one of the symbols of the state, which has its own legal status and is performed in solemn ceremonies accompanied by poetic text and music. The form and meaning of the national anthem reflect the goals and views of the nations and peoples, social groups and classes living in a particular country. The national anthem differs from other musical works in its ideological direction and means of reflection. The National Anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan has gained incomparable importance in all spheres of state life and is an important tool of political propaganda.

The National Anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan - When our national anthem is played abroad with different attitudes, we will have the opportunity to compare it with the national anthems of other countries. It is not for nothing that the saying "to each his own, the moon is visible to his eyes" is said. However, it is not correct to apply this to our national anthem. Because, indeed, Mutal (Mutavakkil) Burkhanov created one of the most perfect examples of the hymn genre in the world. The music of the national anthem lifts the spirit of every Uzbek citizen, cheers up his heart, and strengthens his sense of pride. This music stands out among the hymns of the world with its splendor and perfection. Also, in the music of the anthem, the musical traditions of our ancient ancestors, melodies and melodies were skillfully used.

Mutal Burhanov expressed his opinion about his music imbued with patriotism and heroic spirit in his book of memories called "Treasure of the Heart": we worked hard on it. The work was not wasted. Sitting in the parliament of our independent country as a newly announced candidate, my heart was full of pride. Because I believed that this music will find a place in everyone's heart. Halfway through the song, the applause started...[2]

Now let's pay attention to the comments of Abdulla Oripov, the People's Poet of Uzbekistan, Hero of Uzbekistan, who created the text of the anthem, in May 2001: "The famous composer Mutal Burkhanov is undoubtedly one of the great representatives of the music of the last 20th century. Fortunately, this breed entered the 21st century together with the next generations, which makes us happy. The most important thing is that the independence we have achieved is similar to the great event that happened to Mutal Burhanov. The spirit and intensity of the nation is reflected in the anthem. I was lucky to put his words in their place. If I were to remember the proudest moments in my life, I would first of all recognize the time when I created our national anthem together with Mutal Burkhanov.

Not every piece of music can be an anthem. He is a high pathos that can unite the people and call them to desire. The past, present, and future of the nation and the state

should be embodied in its creation. Thanks to our long-standing creative cooperation with the composer... our purposeful melody, rich in content, intense, national and at the same time oriental anthem was born. Now it belongs to the people, the state. Now it is a political fact. So long as it rings forever, the owner who gave it spirit will never die. His fire and sparks are not extinguished.

If they said where is eternity, I would stand up and point to Mutal Burkhanov".[3]

The author of these notes was lucky enough to meet Abdulla Oripov and Mutal Burkhanov, the authors of the National Anthem of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and talk about the creation of the national anthem of the Fatherland. The artist of Uzbekistan, recipient of the Order of Merit, Mutal Burkhanov would have been 97 years old if he had lived. Our nation remembers the name of this great talent and the owner of the talent, who erected a statue "that cannot be restored by hand" in the city of music during his lifetime. The house where he lived in Bukhara was turned into a museum. In the "Ancient and eternal Bukhara" monument, built on the initiative of the first President, his name is written in golden letters among a group of compatriots who matured in this ancient land and made a great contribution to the development of the country's culture and art. After all, the memory of the composer who praised the great country is always in our hearts!

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